

Work Package 5, Milestone 5.3: First integrated, grid-or-cloud-enabled cryo-EM service

Executive summary

As described in Task 5.1 – Deployment and operation of the West-Life portal, CSIC is expected to proceed with the integration in the VRE of Scipion Web Tools developed at the Instruct Image Processing Center in Madrid, in order to provide end users with a friendly and dynamical entry point to this service, knowledge and support center.

It is also part of this task to investigate and harmonize user authentication and authorization mechanisms (AAI) with the aim of using the common approach presented in deliverable D4.2.

Scipion Web Tools

Scipion Web Tools (SWT) is a web-based set of tools/workflows derived from the Scipion image processing framework specially tailored to non-expert users in need of very precise answers at several key stages of the structural elucidation process.

Scipion Web Tools current deployment on the EGI Federated Cloud

On September 2017 the latest version of SWT was deployed and is currently running in one instance at the CESNET MetaCloud site.

Current server specifications are:

Instance os type: Uuid_enmr_egi_ubuntu_server_14_04_its_fedcloud_warg_135

Instance size: extra_large (8 CPUs and 32 GB RAM)

Instance extra disk storage: 512 GB

Url: <http://scipionwebtools.westlife.fedcloud.eu/m/services/>

Milestone M18

This setup is enough for the current workload of the service but it might be insufficient if use of the service increases, which is expected to happen soon (scientific paper already accepted for publication). Detailed monitoring of the usage will be needed to decide if migration to a more powerful machine on the Federated Cloud is enough, or a mechanism to dynamically adjust the cluster size needs to be put in place in order to optimize the use of cloud resources.

Integration of Scipion Web Tools in the VRE

In contrast to other West-Life services, Scipion Web Tools is more than a Web front end form with a set of backend applications that can run on the grid or cloud. SWT is based on Scipion, which is itself a framework with its own workflow engine embedded and where the Graphical user interface, either desktop or web based, is completely integrated with this workflow model.

As a result it cannot be easily decoupled to perform a clean front end integration on the West-Life VRE while the backend applications are dynamically deployed on grid or cloud resources.

The solution thus has been to deploy SWT on a cloud instance at the EGI Federated Cloud, as explained on the previous section, and linked the services from the VRE portal under Services – Electron Microscopy – Scipion Web Tools.

Integration of common authorization and authentication (AAI) on SWT

Scipion Web Tools (SWT) currently does not implement any authentication mechanism at all. Access is completely open but privacy of a project relies on the privacy of the project URL. This address is not searchable or browsable, and it is the responsibility of the user to track this URL, for example bookmarking it.

SWT should integrate West-Life SSO in such a way that, when a user access the SWT from the VRE where it was already authenticated it should be able to access other West-Life services, such as the common data repository. Besides, if the user did not authenticate on the VRE, SWT should forward to the ARIA SSO portal to do so.

The following image illustrates the whole scenario.

Milestone M18

Work has been started towards this objective, but it is not yet finished, and depends on the other West-Life components present on this scenario.

ScipionCloud VM

Besides the Scipion Web Tools service described above, a ScipionCloud VM is registered at <https://appdb.egi.eu/store/vappliance/scipion.v1.0>. It is distributed as an OVA image able to be deployed into e.g. OpenNebula environment or VirtualBox. It is based on Ubuntu 14.04 and it contains standalone installation of the Scipion software including GPU support plus remote desktop guacamole installed and configured to access the Virtual Machine through a Web Browser.